

INVOLVEMENT OF STUDENTS IN SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES IN SCHOOLS AND ITS IMPORTANCE

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Abstract: This article provides information about the importance of engaging students in spiritual and educational activities in schools. Currently, one of the most priority directions in the field of education is the quality education program. It is necessary to ensure the activeness of students at school and in contests and events at the national level. In this regard, it is necessary to organize various spiritual and educational contests such as "Essay Contest", "Literacy", "Fictional and Prose Works", "Ghazals and Rubaiy" by the school management. In these activities, the student acquires new knowledge, his views on education, his thinking potential, vocabulary increases. Students develop the ability to think freely and speak fluently. Knowledgeable and intelligent students are encouraged. This will increase the students' interest in the activities and gain the understanding of the correct use of opportunities in the field of education.

Keywords: Students' knowledge, spiritual and educational activities, modern science methods in schools, students' potential, students' motivation, pedagogical and psychological approaches.

Introduction

In the process of educating young people, the specific goals and tasks of determining the qualities of spiritual-intellectual development have been developed. Control of the knowledge and mental maturity of pupils and students making and assessment is important at the state level. With that at the same time, to enrich the student's knowledge of the control and evaluation process, they affect personality development and upbringing. The student is responsible for the assessment and assessment of knowledge and what impressions they left on the student, their friends it is necessary to always monitor how they react to their academic achievements and shortcomings. Pupil and student knowledge monitoring and evaluation are carried out regularly during the academic year rating system is introduced to increase, sometimes by accident prevent

inspections and for orderly, continuous evaluation opens up opportunities. In order to attract students to spiritual and educational events in schools, it is necessary to increase the activity of students in various contests and competitions held by the school management based on the interests of students. Pupils can form their knowledge and outlook and gain new knowledge in contests and competitions. Organizational spiritual-educational contests are of great importance in the intellectual growth of students and the development of morally perfect human beings. The role of spiritual activities is incomparable in the development of vocabulary, fluency of speech, potential and behavior of students to become good people and to become good people. Pupils should be encouraged with valuable prizes and certificates by taking leading positions in events and competitions. It helps students to develop their mental activity and work more on their knowledge. Essay competition should be held by the school management. Students can write their sincere thoughts about their country, people and parents in the essay contest. To date, national values and inter-ethnic harmony are preserved in our country, and all necessary conditions exist for further strengthening of our national values. Participation of the young generation in the life of a comprehensively developing society it is important for everyone to introduce them to the national values and spirituality of the Uzbek people, along with historical memories, as well as universal memories. One of the tasks is human values. Therefore, national and universal values are included in the learning and mutual understanding of educational content mutual cooperation and culture of representatives of different nationalities allows to enjoy spiritual wealth. As a result of this approach system, education, age people absorb the cultural wealth of the Uzbek people. That's what education is for the values of Uzbek and world peoples are embedded in its content. National values should appear as a component of individual culture. Firstly, Let's talk about personal culture in the formation of the worldview of young people people, personal culture refers to the set of thoughts of a certain person material and spiritual wealth created by his mind and hands during his life includes the concept of actions related to humanitarianism and compliance with moral and educational requirements. This is the psychological culture of a person creative ideas created by him, national culture, spiritual and moral aspects are manifested adherence to values. A person's psychological culture is his spirituality is a criterion that determines the level of education. Personal characters psychological culture following spiritual and moral qualities of a person relationship is also expressed through the acquisition of adjectives:

faithful, conscientious, faithful and pious, polite and disciplined, well-educated, educated, intelligent, educated and not late for work and striving to enrich his outlook, faithful to promises, not harming people, doing good Not thanking him, respecting the elders, showing respect to the younger, the elderly, respect for women and children, kindness, warmth, modesty, not calling others not to laugh at people's shortcomings, not to make fun of them, not discrimination against the weak, non-interference in work and leisure surrounding people, hospitality, paying attention to one's inner and outer world, observation of speech culture, preservation of public property, physical and spiritual purity, etc. Personal culture unites it with the community, gives it uniqueness opportunity to make many friends. Enrichment of spiritual and moral qualities, self-improvement, ability to teach, control and manage, self-critical approach; worldview should expand and raise the cultural level. National values - national history, lifestyle unity, its future, generations, social caste, nation, consciousness, language, spirituality and culture inextricably linked with, from the point of view of pedagogical and psychological factors education, all the riches of the culture of the Uzbek people, national heritage it is necessary to express the opinions of the living peoples about our ancestors. About tolerance, lifestyle, traditions, customs, norms of social behavior of Uzbekistan and moral values. Education is central to its content should take over the spiritual life of the Uzbek people, the national way of life concepts and information. Including the national education of Uzbeks A special place for information about people's cultural, social, economic and display territorial identity should be distinguished. National values can vary significantly from one country to another. One of the main national values is freedom. National values are often reflected in the laws of the country, reflected in policies, educational programs, cultural expressions and the public events. Understanding national values politicians, leaders and citizens. Because they define the nation's actions and priorities. They are the decision is the basis for policy formulation and management. National values it also plays an important role in the formation and education of national identity citizens' sense of belonging. It is the pedagogical basis of national values principles of education important to the nation or society used in inculcating and is meant to promote valuable values and practices. These are values often includes patriotism, respect for authority, cultural heritage, social concepts such as solidarity and ethical behavior. National and in different countries across cultures, the pedagogical approach to teaching values is different, but usually includes formal education, informal socialization and cultural combination

receives the transmission. Parents and teachers are also responsible for raising students to be educated and free-thinking, and for them to become perfect people in the future. It is a very high honor for this school that students take pride of place in various contests and competitions. We should organize competitions taking into account the interests and wishes of students. Only then will students become spiritual, enlightened and intelligent children. Knowledgeable people never come up with destructive ideas. The Uzbek people have a saying, "Knowledge acquired in youth is like a pattern carved in stone." Schools can organize different competitions. For example, we can organize intellectual intellectual games by selecting essays, rubai and ghazals about the life and work of our great thinkers. These are the best opportunities for students to make good use of their free time and acquire new knowledge. To date, many opportunities and conditions have been created for young people in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Young people can choose their profession based on their interests. Adopted youth strategic models. The main purpose of this is to make good use of free time of young people. A reading competition is also organized. This will further increase the interest of young people in learning.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that while educating students about the importance of engaging in spiritual and educational activities in schools, it is the main task of parents and teachers to educate young people with good thoughts and good deeds. is considered We need to help our children to live smarter and more comfortably than us, to find their place in the future. We need to ensure that our young people use their free time productively. It is necessary to involve students in spiritual and educational events and competitions during their spare time.

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